

TACTICS OF TREATMENT OF LOCALLY ADVANCED STAGES 2b – 3a OF CERVICAL CANCER.

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Despite advances in cancer prevention, screening, diagnosis and treatment cervix, this disease remains one of the most important health problems, representing the fourth most common malignant tumor among women in the world.

The purpose of the study is to evaluate the results 3-year disease-free survival of patients cervical cancer stages IB2–IIIB, treated with the use of neoadjuvant chemotherapy.

Material and methods

A retrospective non-randomized study was conducted in which results of treatment of 70 patients. All patients underwent comprehensive examination using general clinical, laboratory and radiation diagnostic methods. The effectiveness of chemotherapy was assessed 2 weeks after the administration of cytostatics.

The main criterion for tumor response to drug therapy was volume change neoplasms of the cervix, determined by data from clinical examination, ultrasound and MRI. When assessing immediate effectiveness It was found that with intra-arterial chemotherapy the maximum effect was obtained after one course of administration of cytostatics, therefore it was decided to abstain from the 2nd course of NACT, when patients achieve resectability performed radical operations.

Results

Results and discussion In the first subgroup of patients who received 2 courses of NACT with intravenous infusion cytostatics, extended hysterectomy performed in 66 (94.1%) cases. High risk factors in pathological examination surgical material were identified in 33 (49.8%), intermediate risk – in 11 (16.7%), low risk – in 21 (31.5%) cases. Adjuvant chemoradiotherapy was performed in 45 (69%) observations.

Patients with cervical cancer IB2–IIIB stage the following results were obtained; at Stage IB2 cervical cancer recurrence was noted in 1 (7.8%) case, with stage IIB – in 8 (12.9%), with IIIB – in 6 (18.1%) cases. Cumulative relapse-free survival rate was 90.5%, 83.2% and 73.1% respectively.

Conclusion

Analysis showed that with combined radiation therapy 3-year disease-free survival of patients with cervical cancer stages IB2–IIIB varies depending on the stage of the disease, on average accounting for about 49.8 %. In the study, almost 34.8% of patients did not administered adjuvant radiation therapy, which allows you to maintain the possibility of its use in case of relapse of the disease.

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